

REINCARNATE

D6.2 – Dissemination and Communication Interim Report

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Task leader/Main author	Carmen Serna (AUS)
Contributing partners	Natalia Cediél (AUS)
Reviewer(s)	Ilija Ilic (ASI), João Gonçalves (EUR)

Abstract

The present document presents a detailed overview of the dissemination and communication activities implemented during the first 24 months of the project. Dissemination and communications are key elements of Reincarnate and during the first half of the project, several actions have been taken enabling the project to gain visibility and create a robust community concerned and committed with improving the circularity of the construction sector.

Keywords

Construction, Circularity, Waste use, Dissemination, Communication, Agile, Impact, Community.

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
CDW	Construction and demolition waste
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Management
DoA	Description of Action
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EU	European Union
AB	Advisory Board
GA	General Assembly
TUB	Technical University of Berlin
EUR	Erasmus University Rotterdam
TUD	Technical University of Delft
DMO	Demo Consultants

Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills. This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation. Three empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business ecosystem development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains.

All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

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1. Introduction

It is not a secret that part of the success of an innovation depends on the awareness about this innovation. Through an effective dissemination and communication strategy, Reincarnate and its innovations can gain widespread attention. Therefore, a solid dissemination and communication strategy ensures the involvement of relevant stakeholders in the project and can offer opportunities for future development.

The current deliverable provides an overview of all key activities and actions related to dissemination and communication that took place during the first half of the project. It gives an analytic presentation of the performance of our digital channels, our participation in physical and online events, our scientific publications, online articles, etc.

The basis of this document is D6.1 Reincarnate Impact Master Plan that sets the foundations of our strategy. While D6.1 presented a detailed overview of Reincarnate's communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, D6.2 provides proof of the impact created by month 24. Dissemination and communication need to be agile and ready to adapt according to the needs of the project and the overall environment. Therefore, within the document, we showcase the full set of activities carried out in the frame of communication and dissemination frameworks.

In addition, this document provides an overview and criticism of our unique Agile Stakeholder Management Strategy, an open framework of collaboration with peers and groups that can benefit and contribute to the overall impact of the project. We reveal some key activities and interactions that took place during our first 3 Sprints and highlight the key lessons learnt we extracted from this experience.

The efforts described in this report are directly linked to the execution of WP6 – Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation, as described in the Description of Action (DoA).

2. Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Reincarnate partners have devoted significant efforts into communicating and disseminating critical project activities, outcomes and findings to the wider community. This section provides an overview of the performance of Reincarnate’s Dissemination & Communication Strategy as defined in D6.1 Reincarnate Impact Master Plan while presenting all key activities that took place during the first half of the project.

2.1. Overall Strategy performance

Throughout this first 24-month period, dissemination and communication played a significant and crucial role to Reincarnate’s overall workplan and performance. Although both activities are quite interlinked, in Reincarnate we chose to treat them as different but closely depended to each other. Our primary focus has been given into defining the appropriate channels and paths for better reach of our audience and target groups while continuously evaluating and adjusting our strategies and activities based on the response that we had and the first set of outcomes that the project produced.

Figure 1: Dissemination and Communication Strategy Implemented M24

2.1.1. The three phases approach

As previously outlined in Reincarnate’s Impact Master Plan, communication and dissemination activities have been planned in three different phases (Scouting, Interaction and Learning). The common goal was to build and nurture a community and brand around the project, maximise visibility, and engage with stakeholders to foster dialogue and collect feedback on the project’s vision and progress.

In this regard, the timeline followed has been:

- ❑ From M0 to M6 of the project, the project's visual identity and critical brand assets have been created, all Communication and dissemination channels have been set up, and the first mapping of stakeholders has been developed.
- ❑ From M6 to M12, the focus progressively shifted towards establishing a recognisable presence in all our digital channels, beginning the conversation with related initiatives, connecting with other EU-funded projects and working on additional promotional materials and long-form articles to cover the core concepts of the project for a wider audience.
- ❑ From M12 to M24, efforts have increased in event participation and publications, reinforcing the social media campaigns, brainstorming and drafting Reincarnate's value proposition and refining the engagement strategy. During this phase, we joined the Tech4EU
- ❑ Construction Cluster and developed high-quality interviews and promotional material.

As of the creation of this deliverable, the main goal is to keep building the Reincarnate's presence in digital channels, reinforcing its core messages, linking them to upcoming results and fortifying our presence in cluster and ecosystem activities.

In these 24 months, the project consolidated its *online presence*, mobilising a total of 2.380 followers in social media, keeping up a meaningful, steady stream of weekly content with 250.000+ post impressions in social media, 90 blog entries and 24 Zenodo entries overall generating 1.500+ visualizations.

This promotional effort has been boosted by increased participation in key *events, conferences and webinars*. The consortium's commitment to dissemination is also commendable: there are 4 preprints and 4 peer-reviewed and conferences publications.

Of course, all these actions have been supported by a harmonised branding identity and a solid set of *promotional materials*, both in print (e.g. brochures, posters) and digital form (e.g. videos, clips, banners).

The detailed list of Reincarnate's impact KPIs, together with the updated targets at this point, is shown in the following table. A detailed breakdown of the project's metrics (e.g. website, social media) is provided in section 3.

Category	Indicator	Reported M24	KPI
Social media	Size of the online community	2,380	5000
	No. of impressions (monthly)	10'8k	200
Website	No. of unique visitors (monthly average)	102	500
Events	No. of Events participated	19	50
Webinars/ Workshops	No. of Webinars / Workshops	7	10
	No. of Registrations / Participants	425	300
Peer-reviewed publications	Scientific Publications in Journals	4	10
	Scientific Publications in Conferences	0	30
Publications	Awareness Publications	90	40
Newsletters	No. of newsletters contributed/released	12	10
Open access	No. of downloads (total)	1,040	1000

Table 1: Reincarnate KPIs at month 24

2.1.2. Coordination of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Monitoring and adjusting the Dissemination and Communication strategy, on a frequent basis, is a fundamental element of the project's success. During the first half of the project, AUSTRALO, as coordinator of WP6, has continuously coordinated and monitored the dissemination and communication activities allowing the consortium to correct any possible deviations and improve its effectiveness by applying correction and mitigation measures when needed.

For the successful coordination of Task 6.1 (Stakeholder collaboration framework) and Task 6.2 (Dissemination and communication), AUSTRALO is implementing a 6 steps methodology:

1. Design: Design of specific activities based on the Dissemination & Communication Plan and the desired impact.
2. Execute: Execute the action according to plan.
3. Monitor: Closely monitor the activity and collect input and results.
4. Evaluate: Evaluate the outcomes of the activity in a collaborative way according to the desired targets set in the design phase.
5. Learn: Learn through this evaluation and try to extract the most valuable outcomes out of it.
6. Adjust: Absorb findings and lessons learnt and adjust the plan accordingly, if needed.

All outcomes and results of the Dissemination and Communication plan are reported in this deliverable for the 24 first months of the project and will be updated at M48 for the final report at month 48.

Coordination resources:

- To allow us keeping track of all the dissemination and communication activities, AUSTRALO uses a tailored-made monitoring tool (Excel) that compiles every action (planned and done) in the frame of Reincarnate measuring the KPIs achievements and partner's involvement.

The screenshot displays the REINCARNATE D&C Monitoring Tool interface. It features a menu bar at the top with options like File, Edit, View, Insert, Format, Data, Tools, and Extensions. Below the menu is a toolbar with various icons for navigation and editing. The main content area is a large table with columns for indicators, current values, targets, and monthly monitoring data from January to December. The table is organized into sections: VISITORS, TRAFFIC SOURCES, SOCIAL MEDIA (LINKEDIN, TWITTER), and PUBLICATIONS. Each section includes specific metrics such as 'No. of Visitors', 'No. of Unique Visitors', 'No. of Page Views', 'No. of Followers', 'No. of Posts', and 'Peer-reviewed Scientific Publications'. The 'MONTHLY MONITORING' section provides a grid of data for each month, with some cells containing numerical values and others being empty or containing small icons.

Figure 2: Reincarnate D&C Monitoring Tool

- To allow us to have a good internal communication, which is crucial at project level to carry out the dissemination and communication strategy, AUSTRALO dynamizes a channel in Mattermost, the platform that the project uses for internal chatting, deployed on a secure environment that ensures compliance with the project's DMP.

The screenshot shows a Mattermost communication channel titled 'Communication and Dissemination Actions and Activities'. The channel has 26 members and 1 message. The message is from 'carmenserna' at 10:42 AM. The message content is: '@all check the upcoming Newsletter we have prepared! Will be launched soon, so send your comments ASAP to be taken into account. Thank you !!'. Below the text is a PDF attachment titled 'Newsletter #4 REINCAR...' with a size of 2.9MB. The channel name 'February 16' is visible. Below the message, there is another message from 'carmenserna' at 10:15 AM: 'Hello everyone! Are you planning to attend any event / conference / workshop in the following months? Are you in the process of having a new publication released? Please, add your upcoming activities to this excel sheet, for monitoring purposes. Many thanks in advance!'. A URL is provided: 'https://nextcloud.reincarnate-project.eu/index.php/apps/onlyoffice/52423?filePath=%2FReincarnate%2F09%20WP6_Communication%2C%20Dissemination%2C%20and%20Exploitation%2FEvents%20%26%20Publications.xlsx'. At the bottom, there is a link to 'Reincarnate Nextcloud' and a logo for 'Reincarnate Nextcloud' with the text 'Sharing files for Reincarnate'.

Figure 3: Communicate Channel in Mattermost

2.2. Engagement Framework

2.2.1. Agile Stakeholder Management Strategy

Promoting Reincarnate and encouraging stakeholders to engage with the initiative requires understanding who the ‘target audience’ is. Understanding these profiles and their influence in the value chain is essential to crafting the Dissemination and Communication Plans. Therefore, since the beginning of the project we have created a common Stakeholder Ecosystem database, trying to map the different stakeholders relevant for the Reincarnate project. Around 150 stakeholders have been already identified.

As indicated in D6.1, during the first six months of the project, Reincarnate identified the stakeholders to be engaged during the project, schematised in the figure below:

Figure 4: Reincarnate's Stakeholder Groups

As a second step, from M6 to M24, Reincarnate focused on informing and engaging the stakeholders via dedicated activities, via dissemination and communication activities (i.e. newsletters, social media campaigns, events participation, workshops organisation, content creation on the website).

In the table below, a summary of the D&C activities put in place to inform and engage our stakeholders is presented.

ACTIVITY	SCOPE
Events/workshops organised/participated	Thanks to these activities, the consortium could present the project to various stakeholders, informing them about our activities and gathering feedback.
Scientific publications	To reach a more technical audience, with emphasis on RTOs and academia, to share the knowledge acquired by the project and its future applications.
Newsletters & awareness publications	To constantly inform our community about the project advancements and achievements.

Table 2: D&C engagement activities

2.2.2. Reincarnate Advisory Board

As part of the Stakeholder Ecosystem Map, we have set up the Reincarnate Advisory Board (AB). Project partners proposed professionals with recognized experience in the construction industry and we invited 7 individuals to a first AB Meeting that took place on 16th January 2024, who accepted to become members of the Reincarnate AB.

The Advisory Board of Reincarnate comprises seven experts from different fields: science, engineering, economy, business and innovation. The Reincarnate team has nominated them to assist in the project’s technical gatherings, workshops and communication activities. The board will collaborate voluntarily to support Reincarnate’s innovations and research from an external perspective, providing valuable expertise to enhance our project.

We have created a specific section on the website where the seven profiles can be checked: <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/advisory-board/>

Figure 5: First meeting with the Reincarnate AB

3. Dissemination and Communication Activities

The dissemination and communication activities implemented until M24 focused on two main aspects:

- Make the results open and available for the stakeholders to facilitate the usage of them (dissemination activities)
- Promote and increase the visibility of the project activities, achievements, team, etc. (communication activities).

In the following section, a description of the central dissemination and communication activities carried out by the project in the first half of the project is presented, focusing on:

- The digital channels used; including the website, the social media channels and the open access repository.
- The promotional material created.
- The publications; including newsletter, online articles and scientific publications.
- The events/workshops participated/organised.
- The actions carried out in collaboration with stakeholders.

3.1. Digital Channels

Nowadays, digital tools are the backbone of communication between an initiative and its target audience. Reincarnate has devoted significant efforts towards its digital tools, especially social media, not only for exposing its outcomes to the target groups, but also for creating a community around the project interested in Circularity in the Construction sector, therefore establishing Reincarnate as a “recognised” brand where people can visit or follow to find out news about this domain.

Establishing Reincarnate as a brand and building a community of followers around it gives us the opportunity to capitalise on the second half of the project where dissemination of our results and outcomes will be a priority.

3.1.1. Reincarnate Website

Project website <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/>

Reincarnate’s website showcases the project’s main ideas, approach, news, findings, and results from our use cases. It is continuously updated with the project latest news (at M24, we published 90 news, with an average of more than three blog posts per month) and scientific publications. When needed, updates on the content and the Team were also done, like the creation of the Advisory Board and Tech4EU Cluster pages.

Figure 6: Reincarnate webpage

It has been designed following the branding elements set up at the beginning of the project (see D6.7), and it follows this structure:

Home	Project	Innovations	Demonstrators	Team	News	Contact
				Behind Reincarnate		
				Advisory Board		
				Tech4EU Cluster		

In terms of performance, the breakdown of the site’s metrics on Google Analytics is presented below. This overview spans the project’s run so far and shows the aggregated totals from the official launch of Reincarnate’s website (September 2022) to the present moment. During the 24 months under consideration, the website has driven traffic of almost 3.000 users and 9.798 views (400+ average monthly views).

Figure 7: Reincarnate website analytics

The three countries from which most users visit the website are Germany, Ireland, and Poland.

Figure 8: Reincarnate website visitors by country

The pages with the most views in order of relevance are Home (with 2,712 views, 30% of the website traffic), News (796 views) and Team (765 views).

From the first release of the website at M3, some new features were added:

- A new subsection has been added to the Team section, highlighting the Tech4EUconstruction cluster. On this page, the cluster and its leading members are presented.
- A new subsection has been added to the Team section, presenting the members of the Reincarnate Advisory Board. This section, in a very short time has reached a great number of visualizations (53).

Figure 9: New sections in the webpage

3.1.2. Social Media Channels

LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/reincarnate-eu/
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X	https://twitter.com/ReincarnateEU
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YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCsdBzgML1hgZ7L8LC9ddhRA
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Reincarnate maintains an active presence on X, LinkedIn and YouTube with an aggregated audience of 2.380 followers between the three platforms. Social media is a quick and effective way to directly engage with the project's wider audience and other key related initiatives and promote Reincarnate's achievements in publications, events and partners' initiatives.

To keep the audience always interested, the D&C team created different LinkedIn and Twitter campaigns and stories covering various topics:

- #ReincarnateNews: Highlighting project updates on different topics.
- #BehindReincarnate: Referring to the team
- #ReincarnateInnovations: Referring to the social and digital developments in the project
- #ReincarnaTECH: Indicating the technical contents of the project related to the CP-IM Platform
- #ReincarnateInspiration
- #ReincarnaTALKS: Showcasing the project members, talking about the importance of Reincarnate and their contributions (solutions, innovations, demonstrators)
- #FridayQuiz: Engaging with the audience by addressing critical concepts, curiosities, and statistics related to the project's topics.
- #FridayThink: Engaging with the audience by asking questions that encourage reflection.

LinkedIn is Reincarnate's social channel with the most engagement, with a community of 772 followers and 187,257 post impressions.

As far as the content, these are some posts with the most impressions, showing that the audience’s interest is diverse, giving support both to technical and social aspects equally:

Figure 10: Top 3 LinkedIn Posts

With a community of 1,608 followers and 72,267 post impressions, X is the channel with wider reach, allowing the project to promote its activities, results and goals and engage the stakeholders effectively. As for LinkedIn, the D&C team diversified the content published, scheduling weekly posts and diversifying the content, following the social media campaigns presented above.

During the General Assemblies, we have prepared specific live-tweeting stories, showcasing in real time the meeting discussions, inviting followers to stay up to date to any development.

The highest performing tweet, with more than 2,500 views, it is the one releasing the launch version of the CP-IM platform, meaning that the audience in this social media is keen on technical related content. The strategy for the second part of the project will follow this path: more human content related to the technical progress in the project.

Figure 11: Top X Post

YouTube serves as the repository for all the videos published in the project. Once posted there, dedicated promotional activities were scheduled, achieving the following results:

- Number of videos: 28
- Views: 830

Figure 12: Reincarnate YouTube channel

3.1.3. Open Access Repository

Zenodo https://zenodo.org/communities/reincarnate_heurope/

Following the European Commission guidelines for Open Science, Reincarnate provides open access to peer-reviewed publications, public deliverables, brand assets and other resources generated within the project.

A dedicated Zenodo community and repository is already in place for the project, where all sorts of publications (e.g. articles, posters...), press releases and more can be found. Public deliverables will be uploaded on Zenodo and on our website once validated by the European Commission.

Thanks to the promotional strategy set up to make the project's results available to our stakeholders, we achieved more than 1,503 views for the 24 documents uploaded on Zenodo up to month 24.

Figure 13: Reincarnate Zenodo channel

3.2. Promotional Material

3.2.1. Printed material

In the dissemination framework, Reincarnate designed a trifold flyer, a one-pager and a roll-up with two objectives: accompanying email campaigns and be shown offline during conferences and events.

Figure 14: Reincarnate printed material

3.2.2. Multimedia material

To make Reincarnate’s social media posts more engaging and captivating, Reincarnate’s social media manager created a set of short clips to accompany the most relevant posts, such as:

- Reincarnate important announcements and achievements.
- Reincarnate Anniversary.
- Reincarnate General Assemblies (GA).
- Reincarnate events organisations and participations.

Some examples:

- [Behind Reincarnate](#)
- [European Week for Waste Reduction Campaign](#)
- [Women in Science Campaign](#)
- [GA Meeting in Sweden](#)
- [2023 achievements](#)

In addition, during the GA meeting in Sweden, WP6 interviewed some partners to gather material for publishing videos explaining the project, its main activities, impact and benefits. The videos are published on the Reincarnate YouTube channel under the #ReincarnaTalks campaign.

Figure 15: ReincarnaTALKS video interviews

3.3. Reincarnate Newsletter

Newsletters are a simple and effective tool to make the results of the project available for the stakeholders while promoting the main activities of the project.

In the first 24 months, the consortium published four newsletters (M06-M24). The team will keep publishing two newsletters a year except for three newsletters that are planned to be released the last year of the project, as we will have more results to share, focusing more on the technical achievements.

- [Newsletter 1](#): released in December 2022.
- [Newsletter 2](#): released in February 2023.
- [Newsletter 3](#): released in June 2023.
- [Newsletter 4](#): released in February 2024.

The content of each newsletter has been carefully designed to keep the readers interested. Each newsletter has been sent via Brevo (67 subscribers) and published on LinkedIn (368 subscribers) using the LinkedIn Newsletter service. The newsletters can be found both in the project website (News > Newsletters) and the Zenodo repository.

Figure 16: Reincarnate LinkedIn Newsletter

In addition to this, Reincarnate participated in several external newsletters, amplifying its audience and reaching more stakeholders:

- Reincarnate featured at the BIMprove Newsletter, released in October 2022.
- Reincarnate featured at the [ASHVIN Newsletter](#), released in November 2022.
- Reincarnate featured at the [Reincarnate Newsletter](#), released in December 2022.
- Reincarnate featured at the [ASHVIN Newsletter](#), released in March 2023.
- Reincarnate featured at the [Reconmatic Newsletter](#), released in September 2023.
- Reincarnate featured at the [Reincarnate Newsletter](#), released in November 2023.
- Reincarnate featured at the [ASHVIN Newsletter](#), released in March 2024.
- Reincarnate featured at the [Robétarmé Newsletter](#), released in April 2024.

3.4. Press releases

Reincarnate has drafted and published 4 press releases.

- [Reincarnate Project Launch Press Release](#), 29/06/2022
- [BAM Press Release](#), 20/07/2022
- [CEMEX Poland joins European project Reincarnate to extend the life cycle of buildings](#), 20/03/2023
- [Press Release to announce that Reincarnate has joined the Tech4EUconstruction Cluster](#), 02/12/2023

In addition, the project has been featured in 6 media outlets [World Cement](#), [AagNet](#), [Rynek Infrastruktury](#), [Allgemeine Bauzeitung](#) and [1 TV broadcast](#).

Recently, we have managed to release a press release under the BUILD UP platform: [How can we realize a digitally controlled circular construction?](#) This article compiles 8

research developments achieved by Reincarnate, thus maximising their life cycle and determining if they are suitable for reuse.

3.5. Online Articles

Since M01, Reincarnate’s consortium has been active and enthusiastic in producing non-scientific publications promoting the events, publications and activities of the project on our website through online articles. In total by M24, we have published 90 blog articles, showcasing pictures and including statements collected in the different activities.

Reincarnate put a structured editorial calendar in place from the beginning of the project to keep the audience and stakeholders always interested in its activities. We structured the publications as a “series” to continuously diversify the content, tell exciting stories and transfer the knowledge acquired in the project.

The series published until M24 can be regrouped as follows:

Figure 17: Reincarnate News section (categories)

All articles are accessible under the <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/news/>.

3.6. Scientific Publications

Reincarnate has published 4 peer-reviewed scientific publications and 4 pre-print papers. The 8 publications are available in our Open Access Repository.

Category	Title	Date	Status
Pre-print	14 Examples of How LLMs Can Transform Materials Science and Chemistry: A Reflection on a Large Language Model Hackathon	07/2023	Published
Journal	Data-driven of Alkali-activated concrete using Sequential Learning (SL)	09/2023	Published
Journal	Presenting SLAMD - A Sequential Learning Based Software for the Inverse Design of Sustainable Cementitious Materials	09/2023	Published
Pre-print	LLMs can Design Sustainable Concrete – a Systematic Benchmark	01/2024	Published
Pre-print	Beyond Theory: Pioneering AI-Driven Materials Design in the Sustainable Building Material Lab	02/2024	Published
Pre-print	Reincarnate: Shaping a Sustainable Future in Construction Through Digital Innovation	04/2024	Published
Journal	Concreting a sustainable future: A dataset of alkali-activated concrete and its properties	04/2024	Published
Journal	What matters when? – An integrative literature review on decision criteria in different stages of the adaptive reuse process	05/2024	Published

Figure 18: Reincarnate scientific publications

Additionally, Reincarnate has been featured in the latest [SB4EU Smart Buildings EU-funded Innovations Brochure](#). This brochure provides a portfolio of synthetic factsheets concerning 101 EU-funded projects, which have been identified and selected for their particular relevance with the Smart Building topic.

3.7. Events and Workshops

Reincarnate has been prominently featured in 19 events and 7 workshops.

3.7.1. Events

Since M05 and until M24, Reincarnate has participated in 19 events and Conferences. At this stage, the focus has been to give visibility to the project, raise awareness about our role in the industry and connect with industry stakeholders.

Category	Title	Date	Place
Webinar	Trace4Value Project Event	04/10/2022	Online
<p>During the virtual event, Lars Nybom, Group Function Strategy and R&D, and Mikael Lindecranz, solutions architect and project manager at Ragn-Sells, presented our Reincarnate project and shared the main objectives and impacts it will achieve with more than 30 traceability experts.</p>			
Festival	Berlin Science Week	10/11/2022	Online
<p>On 2022 annual gathering, the year of Reincarnate born, our colleague Sabine Kruschwitz from partner Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM) participated at Berlin Science Week explaining how the Reincarnate project will avoid 80% of construction waste through intelligent circular economy.</p>			
Summit	European Week for Waste Reduction	18/11/2023	Online
<p>From 21st to the 25th of November, Reincarnate was one of the promoters carrying out actions in the European Week for Waste Reduction. During this European campaign, Reincarnate has launched one podcast-pill a day leaving a key message: “there are social means and new opportunities for our products, materials, and buildings by establishing a reincarnation practice.”</p>			
Conference	Information Day #horizoneurope	27/01/2023	Warsaw, Poland
<p>During the Information Day about Horizon Europe Programme organised by the Polish National Contact Point (Krajowy Punkt Kontaktowy / Narodowe Centrum Badań i Rozwoju), our team member Piotr Dymarski, Head of Digital Transformation Department at Mostostal Warszawa S.A., participated in the panel “Green, digital, fair – transformation in the framework program Horizon Europe”, which was moderated by Marcin Popkiewicz, Chairman of the monitoring committee of Green Deal projects</p>			

Convention	RILEM Convention and 4th International Congress on Materials & Structural Stability	10/03/2023	Rabat, Morocco
<p>At the convention, the BAM team engaged in discussions with academics, researchers, industrialists, testing laboratories, and authorities to explore how artificial intelligence (AI) could facilitate the development of sustainable building materials.</p>			
Conference	openBIM Poland 2023	18/05/2023	Warsaw, Poland
<p>During the conference, Reincarnate had the chance to be shared among the audience as an innovative project leading the transition towards a green and circular construction sector. On a first interaction, Jorge Camilo Díaz Garcia, from CEMEX Global, explained how digital tools can support the path to CO2 neutrality. On a second interaction, our colleagues Alicja Kuczera, from Polish Green Building Council, and Piotr Dymarski, from Mostostal Warszawa SA, participated together with Henryk Kwapisz and Jorge Camilo Diaz Garcia in an interesting panel addressing different solutions to minimize the carbon footprint.</p>			
Conference	Sustainable Places (SP2023)	16/06/2023	Madrid, Spain
<p>During 14 and 15 of June 2023, our partners DEMO Consultants (Netherlands), Mostostal Warszawa (Poland) and 3L Arquitects (Germany) have attended in person technical sessions and project-organized workshops around technology transfer, renewable energy implementations and energy security with the aim of facilitating actions that increase the rate of renovation and renewable energy implementations.</p>			
Forum	Polish Real Estate Forum 2023	20/06/2023	Sopot, Poland

Last 19-20 June, our partner Polish Green Building Council PLGBC was participating at the Polish Real Estate Forum 2023. The conference was a two-day event and Dorota Bartosz, PhD, Director for Sustainable Construction at PLGBC and representatives of PLGBC Members participated at the panel “Green added value – circular economy, building adaptations, ESG” relevant to Reincarnate.

Conference	ERES Annual Conference	12/07/2023	London, UK
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From the 12th to the 15th of July, the 29th ERES Annual Conference London 2023 was held, which is the leading real estate research meeting in Europe and one of the most significant property-related conferences globally. The Reincarnate project was represented by PhD researcher Brian van Laar from partner TUDelft, who presented the paper “A comprehensive literature review on the decision criteria for adaptive reuse throughout the AR process.”

Conference	DIGICON 2023	14/09/2023	Munich, Germany
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The DIGICON 2023 convention, titled “The digital city of the future – New opportunities for your business model”, was held in Munich on September 13th and 14th. It is the annual event of Digitale Stadt München e.V. and is one of the major conferences on digitalization

topics in the Munich Metropolitan Region. At the conference, Dr Christoph Völker, from our partner Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM), showcased SLAMD, the open-source app they bring to the Reincarnate project digital innovations (10) for circular materials.

Summit	PLGBC Green Building Summit	6/10/2023	Warsaw, Poland
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On October 5th and 6th, the PLGBC Green Building Summit was held in Poland. It is the international sustainable building conference where keynote speakers of the industry share best practices and inspiration to learn and improve. Two Reincarnate partners were actively coordinating this important summit in the country, PLGBC as the main organizer and CEMEX Poland as a supporting partner.

Conference	Horizon 4 Poland 2023	21/11/2023	Warsaw, Poland
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Last 21-22nd of November took place the Horizon4Poland event in Warsaw. Organised by the Łukasiewicz Research Network and the Industry Focal Points (ICP), the event addresses business and the scientific industry. Alicja Kuczera, Chair of the GBC CEO Network at the World Green Building Council and CEO at PLGBC, presented our aim to develop a sustainable built environment.

Committee	Standardization Committee Building Information Modelling (BIM)	26/01/2024	Vienna, Austria
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Reincarnate was presented at the Austrian Standards Standardization Committee Building Information Modelling (BIM) meeting on January 26th. The meeting was attended by about 50 representatives from public authorities, construction companies, software companies, research institutions, infrastructure managers, architects and civil engineers, and other stakeholders.

Webinar	Reconmatic Clustering Event: Promoting Circularity in Construction	28/02/2024	Online
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In this clustering event, sustainability experts and key stakeholders in construction, IT, automation, business and communication disciplines were brought together to provide an overview of the European priorities for the Twin Transition in the sector and identify collaboration opportunities between several research initiatives with similar goals. Representatives from Beeyonders, CircularB COST, Reincarnate, RobetArme, REDOL and Valrec joined the RECONMATIC project, in a discussion panel that aspires to pave the path to independent collaboration workshops on specific research topics.

Summit	Building Smart International Summit 2024	12/03/2024	Valencia
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Our colleague Piotr Dymarski, leading the Digitalization and Innovation Office at Mostostal Warszawa S.A., attended the summit on behalf of the Polish delegation and gathering insights for the Reincarnate project, he sought to establish synergies with stakeholders and gain valuable knowledge.

Convention	RILEM Spring Convention 2024	14/04/2024	Milan
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At the RILEM Spring Convention 2024, held in Milan, Italy from April 10th to 12th, we were honored to present our latest research and promote the visibility of the Reincarnate Project. After last year's successful presence in Morocco, this year three researchers from Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM) graced the Palazzo Mezzanotte with their contributions. Ghezal Ahmad Zia, Sabine Kruschwitz and Christoph Voelker presented Reincarnate's latest research on circular economy and construction materials.

Conference	Reinventing the City: Blueprints for Messy Cities	23/04/2024	Amsterdam
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<p>Representing the Reincarnate project, PhD Researcher at the Technical University of Delft (TUD) Brian Van Laar presented his research “Towards Desirable Futures for the Circular Adaptive Reuse of Buildings: The Combination of Cross-Impact Balance Analysis with Participatory Workshops.”</p>			
Fair	IFAT Munich 2024	13/05/2024	Munich
		<p>From May 13th to 17th, IFAT Munich 2024 took center stage as the premier global trade fair for water, sewage, waste, and raw materials management. At this international event, our colleagues Lars Nybom and Camilla Sonnentheil, from partner Ragn-Sells (RS), representing the Reincarnate project, seized the opportunity to connect with industry leaders and delve into the latest innovations in environmental technology and recycling.</p>	
Conference	Open BIM Poland 2024	16/05/2024	Munich
<p>Following the successful presentation of Reincarnate at the first edition, our partners from PLGBC, CEMEX Polska and Mostostal Warszawa attended the conference to continue promoting our more sustainable and digital innovations.</p>			

Table 3: List of events

All events and conferences are featured in the project website in the news section, by selecting the [events category](#).

3.7.2. Workshops

During the first half of the project, Reincarnate has organised or participated in 7 workshops in total. The team celebrated internal workshops in Gothenburg, Stockholm, the Netherlands and also online to discuss WP developments. In addition, we participated in external workshops like the one organised by the Centre for Entrepreneurship of the Technical University of Berlin (TUB).

Title	Date	Place
First workshop to showcase the launch version of the Reincarnate CP-IM platform	10/02/2023	Online
	<p>The consortium celebrated an internal workshop to showcase the launch version of the Reincarnate CP-IM platform. Led by DEMO Consultants, all 16 partners participated with a total of 25 team members.</p>	
Roundtable: Circular economy in the construction industry	23/05/2023	Berlin
<p>Reincarnate participated in a dynamic discussion about several aspects of the circular economy and recycling in the construction sector together with two others inspiring speakers. At the roundtable, representatives from research and practice came together to exchange ideas about the potential of green solutions to reduce the construction and demolition waste and to make the construction industry sector more sustainable.</p>		
PlanB celebrates a two-day workshop to address Reincarnate challenges using a Scrum framework	11/05/2023	Gothenburg
<p>The workshop has been organised in the framework of the Active Construction Waste Reduction task of the project, whose mission is to develop the Lean Construction Resource Planning concepts and methods for active waste reduction during construction work.</p>		
Reincarnate holds a workshop on the innovations for adaptive reuse-	08/09/2023	Rotterdam

<p>recycling and social-market innovations in Rotterdam</p>		
<p>Reincarnate team convened in Rotterdam to conduct the “WP3 and WP4 Strategy Workshop” on innovative methods for adaptive reuse, recycling and social and market innovations for the project. Participants included members from Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR), Technical University of Delft (TUD), Demo Consultants (DMO), as well as other Reincarnate partners, students and professionals from the business world. The aim was to align strategic priorities for Reincarnate.</p>		
<p>Reincarnate hosts a workshop on Sustainable Practices in Adaptive Reuse and Recycling in Sweden</p>	<p>07/11/2023</p>	<p>Stockholm</p>
<p>On November 7th, partners Ragn-Sells and Plan B gathered at the Väderholmen office near Stockholm, Sweden, to hold a workshop. The focal point of the workshop was the discussion of processes for product and component reuse, as well as parameters to evaluate reusability. This initiative aligns with the adaptive reuse and recycling framework of WorkPackage 3 (WP3), led by the Technical University of Delft.</p>		
<p>#1 Exploitation Workshop Series: Framework and Methodology</p>	<p>14/02/2024</p>	<p>Online</p>

Demo Consultants (DMO), represented by Samaneh Rezvani and Eren Çavuşoğlu, organised the first workshop in the Reincarnate's exploitation series. The workshop series is designed to present insights, reflect on the exploitable results of our work and encourage collaborative exploration among the team with the main objective of increasing the project impact and ensuring acceleration of market uptake of Reincarnate.

Exploring standardization: Insights from Reincarnate's webinar

27/02/2024

Online

In a webinar held on February 27th, Michael Salomon and Stefan Wagmeister from partner Austrian Standards (ASI) explained the role of standardization. The session aimed to present the process of standardization and its importance in making the results of Research & Innovation Projects, like Reincarnate, accessible to a diverse audience.

Table 4: List of workshops

All workshops are featured in the project website in the news section, by selecting the [events category](#).

3.8. Stakeholder Collaboration

One of the results of the Stakeholder Ecosystem Map has been to identify and connect with other Horizon Europe projects and exploit common synergies together for mutual support and growth. In this sense, we have carried out the following actions during the first 18 months:

- Social Media Campaign promoting EU projects that inspired Reincarnate: in this campaign we promoted projects such as [ASHVIN](#), [P2ENDURE](#), [BIMSPEED](#), [Interreg North-West Europe CHARM](#), [The Circular Kitchen](#), [INSITER](#) and LIBS-ConSort.
- Reincarnate signed a [MoU with StandICT.eu](#) project.

- Reincarnate established formal collaboration with its sister project [Reconmatic](#).
- Reincarnate has joined the [Tech4EUConstruction cluster](#), committed to digitalising and automatising the European construction sector, making it safer and greener, and enlarging its scope through the initiative. Leading the cluster, European projects [BEEYONDERS](#), [RoBétArmé](#) and [Reincarnate](#) have officially welcomed Reincarnate to tackle critical challenges in the construction sector collaboratively. Other projects have recently joined the Cluster: InCUBE, Reconmatic, HERON and BIM2Twin.
- Reincarnate established formal collaboration with [CIRCULOOS](#) project.

Figure 19: Promotional banner: Reincarnate joins the Tech4EUConstruction cluster

4. Next steps

The primary purpose of the dissemination is to make the project results available to the stakeholders and to transfer the knowledge acquired to them.

During the second half of the project, where the results and technologies of Reincarnate will be more mature, the partners will increase their efforts to ensure all the stakeholders will be aware of the project's outcomes and activities.

From M24 to M48, the following activities will be reinforced:

- Participation in events, conferences, and workshops: Reincarnate will participate in events and present the results - *to reach the KPI of more than 50 events participated/organised*. When writing this deliverable, Reincarnate

received the acceptance confirmation, for the second year in a row, to participate in the Sustainable Places Conference 2024.

- Peer-reviewed publications: as reported in this deliverable, four publications have already been published. Reincarnate will reinforce this task and continue submitting papers, with more emphasis in the last part of the project to make the final results available to our stakeholders. In particular, there are currently publications planned on Communication Barriers to Adoption (by partner EUR), Adaptive upscaling approach for assessing materials' circularity potential with non-destructive testing (NDT) (by partner BAM).
- Cluster activities: we will invest specific effort in reinforcing the engagement activities, especially the ones related to the Tech4EUConstruction cluster and the newly created Circular Construction cluster. More Horizon Europe projects will be contacted, and joint dissemination activities, such as promotional campaigns, and the organisation of joint events, workshops and papers, will be reinforced. In addition, the Exploitation managers of each project will also be invited to participate in the cluster meetings to gain knowledge on the exploitation and business developments of each project's main Key Exploitable Results.
- Social media campaigns and blog posts: In the coming 24 months, we will change a bit the focus: from M1 to M24, the main scope of this activity was to present the project, its partners, the people involved, the goals, and the first achievements. Since the project is entering a more mature phase, more emphasis will be dedicated to disseminating and promoting the project's technical accomplishments via ad hoc campaigns and blogs, in close collaboration with the technical WPs. Meetings with the WP leaders will be organised to schedule content creation properly.
- Community of Practice: keep profiling and identifying Target Groups -and the specific contact points- with relevance for the activities of the project with the ambition to expand the Reincarnate community of practice.
- Increase Reincarnate' s presence online: specific effort will be dedicated to reaching an online community of 5,000 by the end of the project. To do so, the project will diversify the social media campaigns, amplifying the joint activities with the different clusters and initiatives.

5. Conclusion

The current deliverable foresaw to update the dissemination and communication strategy, and to present the activities that took place during the first 24 months of the project. In parallel, it aimed to present a short but solid overview of the agile stakeholder management strategy and extract some valuable insights from it. Adding to the above, a discussion on all key quantified targets and Key Performance Indicators (KPI's), which constitute the means of evaluation and assessment for the performed activities, was presented.

Last but not least, we provided a set of actions that mark the way forward with the communication strategy, to face the second half of Reincarnate.

In conclusion, during the first half of the project, several major anticipated activities were implemented according to the plan, with no deviations. The consortium is very satisfied with the performance results achieved so far regarding the dissemination and communication activities. As lessons learnt, when it comes to stakeholder engagement, identifying and engaging stakeholders from the beginning is key since their input provides valuable insights and support for the project. The project has managed to build a solid and engaged online community and this means that we are targeting the right stakeholders. In addition, regarding to risk management, it is important to highlight the need from the Communication team to be prepared to adapt to changes and unexpected challenges, following all project partners activities. Flexibility and the ability to pivot when necessary are crucial for overcoming lack or abundance of activity.

Finally, this report will be updated in month 48 of the project, which will include the updated dissemination and communication strategy, the description and evaluation of actions until the end of the project and any sustainability measures, we might foresee, for our most successful communication results.